

Gypsum (Marine) Reduction with Kutch Lignite*

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(Manuscript received 25 October 1971; revised 24 January 1972; accepted 28 March 1972)

The decomposition of marine gypsum has been studied at the laboratory stage with Kutch lignite. The experimental ratio for gypsum to fixed carbon in the lignite is 1 : 2. The reaction is completed in less than 30 min at 800°C. With higher percentage of lignite, the small amount of sulphur in the lignite leads to sulphide formation.

SULPHUR is an important raw material for many essential and strategic industries. No sulphur deposits have been located so far in India and almost all the requirements of sulphur are met by imports¹. Gypsum and pyrites have been recommended as potential alternative sources for sulphur/sulphuric acid. Plants for the production of sulphuric acid from pyrites are under erection at Amjor and Udaipur.

In recent communications^{2,3,4}, the authors have evaluated the feasibility of several methods for production of sulphuric acid from gypsum under Indian conditions. In all the suitable methods the gypsum is first reduced to calcium sulphide^{5,6,7} by coke/coal or lignite at high temperature, 900°C being the optimum temperature.

Fairly good deposits of gypsum are located⁸ in Kutch district of Gujarat (Table 1). Besides, nearly 25,000 tons of good marine gypsum is available annually from the salt works in Kutch.

Recently massive deposits of lignite have been found in the Kutch district of Gujarat. Table 2 gives the characteristics^{9,10} of Kutch lignite. Because of its low calorific value the lignite from Kutch is generally considered inferior to the one found elsewhere in the country. Table 3 gives the analysis of coke/coal and lignite used by earlier workers and the Kutch lignite used by the authors for the reduction of marine gypsum.

In view of (i) the inferior quality of Kutch lignite, (ii) the indefinite nature of the reduction of gypsum to calcium sulphide, and (iii) the potential demand of calcium sulphide, it was considered necessary to examine the reduction of marine gypsum, using Kutch lignite.

Experimental

The marine gypsum and Kutch lignite were pulverised to pass 50-100 mesh and mixed in different

TABLE 1. CHARACTERISTICS OF KUTCH GYPSUM

	CaO %	SO ₃ %	H ₂ O %	SiO ₂ %	R ₂ O ₃ %	MgO %	Estimated reserves; lakh tons
Eastern Kutch	32.52	46.45	20.90	—	0.10	traces	9.01
Western Kutch	31.02	45.36	18.64	1.16	1.91	traces	11.07

TABLE 2. CHARACTERISTICS OF KUTCH LIGNITE

Place of lignite deposit in Kutch District	Moisture %	Volatile matter %	Fixed carbon %	Ash %	Calorific value k.cal/k.gm	Quantity of lignite available
1. Umarsar	27.89	37.98	21.91	12.72	4182	11.0 million tonnes
2. Mata-nomadh	11.71	41.07	26.02	20.05	4181	33.0 ,, ,,
3. Jhulrai-Waghpadar	—	—	—	—	—	3.0 ,, ,,
4. Panandhro	8.4	42.8	36.5	12.3	5540	94.0 ,, ,,
5. Akrimota	—	—	—	—	—	41.0 ,, ,,
6. Lakhpat Dhedadi	34.82	33.36	23.40	8.50	3814	12.0 ,, ,,

* This paper was presented in the Applied Chemistry Section of Convention of Chemists, Madras, 1970.

molar ratios of gypsum to carbon, calculated on the basis of fixed carbon in lignite. Small balls of mixtures were made with the help of water. The balls were air dried before heating in the furnace. Table 4 gives the results obtained.

TABLE 3. ANALYSIS OF COAL/LIGNITE USED BY DIFFERENT WORKERS AND THE AUTHORS FOR THE REDUCTION OF GYPSUM

Source	Moisture %	Volatile matter %	Fixed carbon	Ash %	Ref.
Kothaguden coal	5.00	26.40	49.00	19.60	6
Coke	2.50	10.60	65.60	21.30	6
Palana lignite	30.50	35.80	27.10	6.60	6
Coal	1.75	24.71	57.59	16.00	7
Coal	1.80	31.49	51.66	15.05	7
Neyveli lignite	24.24	36.89	35.62	3.35	10
Kutch lignite*	34.82	33.36	23.40	8.50	10

* Kutch lignite is known to have sulphur, both Organic and Inorganic.

TABLE 4. MARINE GYPSUM REDUCTION WITH LIGNITE

Molar Ratio G/L	% Reduction (time 30 min)			% Reduction (time 60 min)		
	700°C	800°C	900°C	700°C	800°C	900°C
1 : 0.65	13.40	32.13	54.56	18.92	59.28	15.62
1 : 1.3	55.51	79.00	85.70	62.30	75.72	52.80
1 : 2.0	79.80	83.56	94.92	52.16	70.42	47.40
1 : 2.7	68.40	82.20	85.40	62.73	84.96	79.96
1 : 5.4	72.55	100.00	100.00	55.15	96.40	92.90
1 : 8.0	82.40	100.00	100.00	64.26	93.46	83.60

The calcium sulphide formed was analysed by decomposing with hydrochloric acid and absorbing the liberated hydrogen sulphide in standard iodine solution; the calcium sulphide was then computed from the amount of hydrogen sulphide evolved after accounting for the fixed ash content of the lignite.

Results and Discussion

The results presented in the Table 4 show that the time and temperature of reaction are the important factors which affect the reaction

The reduction is completed in a short time. According to the stoichiometric ratio, two molecules of carbon are required for the reduction of one molecule of gypsum. Therefore, when Kutch lignite is used as a reducing agent, the theoretical gypsum to lignite (fixed carbon) ratio (by weight) works out to 7 : 4. The data in Table 4 show that the reaction is almost completed with stoichiometric molar ratio of the reductant at 800°C. When the amounts of carbon are increased to more than the theoretical requirements, there is a tendency to approach 100% reduction or even exceed it. This is due to the presence of 2–8% sulphur in Kutch lignite.

The Kutch lignite, requiring a temperature of 800°C, is a better reductant than either coke or coal which requires a temperature of 900°C for the same reaction. The lignite used by the authors has less ash content (Table 3) than either coke or coal and, therefore, the reduced product is less contaminated than when coal or coke is used as a reducing agent.

The reduction of gypsum to calcium sulphide by lignite being a solid phase reaction is expected to be a slow¹¹ reaction. Actually, the reaction is very fast (it is completed in 30 min), thus indicating the formation of either a gas or a liquid phase during the course of the reaction¹². Therefore, it seems that at 800°C, a gypsum molecule dissociates and produces sulphur dioxide, which in turn reacts with carbon, forming carbon dioxide and active sulphur which immediately reacts with gypsum and forms calcium sulphide.

The intermediate reactions postulated above are responsible for the fast rate and the bulk character of the overall reaction. The possibility of sulphur present in Kutch lignite taking part in the reaction cannot be ruled out. Further work on the kinetics and thermodynamic consideration is necessary before finalising the exact mechanism of the reaction.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Dr. D. J. Mehta, Scientist-in-Charge, CSMCRI, for the interest taken during the course of investigation. The authors also thank the Directorate of Geology & Mining, Government of Gujarat, for the supply of lignite.

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